

Graphical Abstract

Spatial-temporal Analysis of Green Hydrogen Production in Lao PDR

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Highlights

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- Optimisation of least-cost hydrogen production with integrated hydropower.
- Hydropower potential is modelled using ERA5 runoff and empirical generation data.
- Hydrogen production costs are lowest (US\$3.9/kg) in wet years with alkaline electrolyser.
- Runoff variability in Laos can double hydrogen production costs in dry years.
- Accounting for electricity demand increases hydrogen costs, favouring southern Laos.

Spatial-temporal Analysis of Green Hydrogen Production in Lao PDR

Lukas Schirren^{a,*}, John Ward^b, Sounthisack Phommachanh^c, Adam Hawkes^a, Vignesh Sridharan^a

^a*Department of Chemical Engineering, Imperial College London, United Kingdom*

^b*Mekong Region Futures Institute, Thailand*

^c*Faculty of Engineering, National University of Laos, Lao PDR*

Abstract

The Government of Laos continues to expand its hydropower fleet, leveraging water resources to increase renewable electricity generation. Electricity exports are crucial for government revenue and poverty alleviation, yet wet season surpluses remain underutilised due to an incomplete cross-border grid and limited domestic demand. Take-or-pay power purchase agreements (PPA) and costly imports in the dry season have contributed to Électricité du Laos' (EDL) US\$5.7 billion debt in 2024. Debt repayment schedules do not align with projected revenues, while planned dams are not optimally located for grid integration. Decarbonised hydrogen production by electrolysis is a government strategy to commercialise surplus electricity, reduce debt, and diversify industry. This study takes a spatial-temporal optimisation approach to identify the least-cost green hydrogen production sites. The model evaluates electrolyser technology, runoff data, time period, and local electricity demand. The results show a minimum levelised cost of hydrogen (LCOH) of US\$3.9/kg of hydrogen by 2030.

Keywords: Electricity exports; Hydropower; Hydrogen; Whole Energy Systems Modelling; Climate Change

*Corresponding Author. Department of Chemical Engineering, Imperial College London, Imperial College Rd, South Kensington, London SW7 2AZ.
E-mail address: lukas.schirren@imperial.ac.uk

1. Introduction

Addressing climate change presents numerous challenges, and although renewable energy sources offer a solution to decarbonise the power grid, it has been more challenging in hard to abate energy-intensive industries, like fertiliser production [1]. Hydrogen has multiple uses in these industries and is predominantly produced by steam-methane-reforming (SMR) [2, 3]. SMR is a carbon intensive process, producing between 7.5 and 12 tons of CO₂ for every ton of hydrogen generated [4, 5]. In 2023, hydrogen production resulted in emissions of 920 Mt of CO₂, making its decarbonisation essential [5]. Green hydrogen based on electrolysis is a viable substitute for SMR [6]. It also enables the use of surplus electricity produced by renewable energy sources [7, 8]. Consequently, the cost of green hydrogen is reduced in regions with high yields from renewable resources [9].

Since 2022, Lao PDR (Laos) has been ranked as the second largest net exporter of electricity worldwide [10]. Approximately 75% of the electricity generated is exported to neighbouring countries, mainly due to the vast availability of hydropower [11, 12]. Although it has one of the lowest per capita electricity use rates in Southeast Asia, the energy intensity of its economy exceeds that of other Southeast Asian countries [13]. Since 1990, there has been significant development in hydropower capacity to address the energy needs of Laos and surrounding regions [14]. The income generated from this development has played a role in reducing poverty and contributes substantially to the socio-economic progress of Laos [14]. Wet season surpluses are neither fully utilised nor commercialised due to a combination of an incomplete cross-border grid and limited domestic commercial and industrial demand. The take or pay of power purchase agreements (PPA) between the Electricité du Laos (EDL) and independent dam operators, combined with expensive electricity imports to meet dry season deficits, have contributed to a debt of 2024 US \$5.7 billion in EDL [15]. EDL's timeline for significant debt repayments is mismatched with expected revenue, and the proposed dam sites for fulfilling both domestic and export requirements do not align with cross-border grid connections. Temporal and spatial factors, along with a depreciated Lao Kip and inflation, suggest continued surpluses in renewable electricity and firm levels of EDL debt [16].

Laos economy is mainly driven by agriculture, with more than two thirds of its population involved in the agricultural sector [17]. The primary crops cultivated, rice and maize, both require the use of nitrogenous fertiliser such

as urea. In 2022, the price of urea more than doubled, exceeding 800 USD per ton, as a consequence of the Russian invasion of Ukraine [18]. Together with the depreciation of the Laotian Kip, this increase caused a notable economic shock, making fertilisers unaffordable to local farmers, which negatively affected crop yield, impacting food security.

Domestic hydrogen production offers a simultaneous solution to both challenges. Improve stability against future fluctuations in fertiliser prices by producing domestic hydrogen-based nitrogen fertiliser and increase the value of generated electricity by producing subsequent products. The worldwide demand for fertilisers is expected to increase due to the expanding global population. Urea, a vital element on the nitrogen fertiliser market, is of significant relevance, especially in the countries of Southeast Asia [19]. The abundance of water in the Mekong, coupled with electricity production via hydropower, positions Laos as an optimal location for the generation of green hydrogen. Producing decarbonised hydrogen via electrolysis is a current Government strategy to utilise and commercialise seasonal surplus generation, reduce EDL's debt and diversify the country's industrial and manufacturing base [16]. Additionally, there is international interest in Laos, as demonstrated by a collaboration with Australia to explore the possibilities of a domestic hydrogen sector [20]. Following this, a deeper analysis of potential sites within Laos is necessary.

In the context of green hydrogen production, it is crucial to regard the geospatial component as the required inputs, electricity and water, must be in proximity to the production site. The identification of least-cost hydrogen production sites has been done in other literature. A study has been conducted for hydrogen production in Iceland by [21], based on the approach of [22]. [23] introduced a multi-criteria approach for solar hydrogen, and [24] developed a framework that integrates factors such as the economy, technology, society and environment for site selection. For wind-based hydrogen, [25] applied a modified strategy. For western countries, such as Germany, [26] performed a geospatial analysis of the hydrogen supply chain for Germany, considering different transportation and storage solutions, resulting in specific infrastructure layouts. This could be done because of the high availability of data. For developing countries, this is often a key drawback for deep geospatial analysis.

The GeoH2 model, created by [27] and advanced by [28], uses photovoltaic and wind data and is applicable globally, particularly benefiting developing countries by using open source data such as global solar irradiation and wind

speed, thus mitigating data scarcity. It divides a country into hexagonal sections, each associated with a Levelised Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH). Consequently, it can pinpoint hexagons with minimal costs as potential production sites. This model is particularly effective in evaluating sites in data-limited developing countries, offering a basis for least-cost production analysis. In Laos, the integration of hydropower plants is essential because hydropower serves as the primary source of electricity.

The objective of this research is to significantly advance the existing GeoH2 model, enabling the identification of the least-cost sites for hydrogen production in Laos. This adaptation requires the incorporation of hydropower, given its extensive availability in Laos. In addition, mountainous terrain and protected areas must be considered for the development of renewable energy. The model results will be evaluated on the basis of four drivers: electrolyser technology, runoff data, time period, and electricity demand. The type of electrolyser influences the efficiency and cost of hydrogen production, which is relevant to the seasonality of hydropower because of the varying baseloads. Different runoff data is necessary because the direct hourly hydropower potential affects electrolysis efficiency. The time period is considered to assess cost reductions and rising electricity demand. Considering spatially varied electricity demand provides a more accurate picture. This research is the first to analyse least-cost hydrogen production sites in Laos. This is partly due to limited data, alongside the recent progress and rising interest in hydrogen production within Laos. The analysis of hydropower production was carried out with data provided by the Laotian Ministry of Energy and Mines (MEM) for the purpose of this study. The next chapter gives an overview of the newly developed methods. Chapter 3 examines the relevant findings from modelled scenarios, with a discussion following in Chapter 4. In Chapter 5, a conclusion is provided.

2. Methods

The research employs and improves the GeoH2 model, developed by [27, 28], an open source framework that applies a spatial optimisation on a hexagonal grid to minimise the LCOH for each hexagon. Spatial data is used to determine the land availability of wind and solar resources, followed by optimising the power system within each individual hexagon using Python Power System Analysis (PyPSA) [29]. PyPSA is designed for the optimisation and analysis of power and energy systems in Python. Figure 1 shows the endogenous variables involved in the optimisation process, covering the determination of the capacities for generation, production, storage, and transportation. Furthermore, a specific state of hydrogen is chosen for transport. This research expands the options for renewable resources by in-

Figure 1: Endogenous variables in the GeoH2 model with addition shown in green.

tegrating hydropower with the spatial ERA5 data set and is reproducible for implementation in other countries [30]. The availability of hydropower for green hydrogen production is determined on the basis of the hourly electricity demand observed in Laos. Additionally, the GeoH2 model has been enhanced with two new preprocessing steps: optimised hexagon coverage and slope-based exclusions. The supplementary material provides a detailed explanation of the buffering process employed to achieve optimised hexagon coverage.

2.1. Land Availability for Wind and Solar Parks

In GeoH2, the placement of individual wind turbines and photovoltaic panels is facilitated by using the Geospatial Land Availability for Energy

Systems (GLAES) tool [31], which systematically identifies regions suited for renewable energy generation. Exclusions are based on coastal areas, herbaceous wetlands, built-up areas, permanent water bodies, agricultural lands, national biodiversity conservation areas, and forest protection areas. Laos is highly mountainous and an additional exclusion of land based on a slope threshold is required to produce realistic results. The slope is determined using a digital elevation model (DEM), which provides a raster representation of altitude. Pre-processing the DEM through smoothing is essential to reduce abrupt altitude fluctuations that could otherwise compromise the outline of the excluded regions. A Gaussian filter is applied to suppress high frequency, which corresponds to rapid changes in altitude within the DEM [32]. This is further explained in the supplementary material.

Wind Energy Exclusion Function. The evaluation of wind energy potential is conducted by applying a threshold condition to the computed slope matrix. In [33] multiple studies are compared, which considered a maximum range for slopes between 10-30%, equal to around 5-17°. [34] considered a maximum slope of 10 % while [33] considered 15% the upper limit as feasible for wind turbines. In [35] the upper limit was even 16.5°. Here, a slope of 15% equal to 8.53° is taken as the maximum slope in all orientations, which excludes 78.02% of the feasible area as shown in Figure 2b.

The predominant wind direction in Laos from 2016 to 2024 is east [36]. Consequently, wind turbines are orientated to maximise power output towards this orientation, following the guideline established by Patel’s rule of thumb [37]. The optimal placement for wind turbines is a separation of around 10 rotor diameters in the optimal direction, and 4 rotor diameters in the perpendicular direction [38, 37]. Here, a Vestas V80 - 2 MW with a diameter of 80 m is considered [39].

Solar Energy Exclusion Function. In the context of solar energy, it is crucial to account for the orientation of the panel. The varying effectiveness of PV installations is captured by associating a higher slope threshold to the south aspect, which receives more solar insolation. For the north-east-west aspect, a lower slope threshold is set. The exclusion mask for PV is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mask}_{pv} = & [(Aspect \in [45^\circ, 135^\circ] \vee Aspect \in [225^\circ, 315^\circ]) \wedge \\ & (Slope \geq \text{Threshold}_{\text{north_east_west}})] \vee \\ & [(Aspect \in [135^\circ, 225^\circ]) \wedge (Slope \geq \text{Threshold}_{\text{south}})] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where the threshold is defined based on the north-east-west and southern aspects.

There is no universally recognised maximum slope for the effective installation of photovoltaic (PV) panels. According to [40], a gradient of up to 11%, equivalent to 6.28° , is considered acceptable, but a gradient less than 1% is optimal. For south-facing photovoltaic panels, a higher inclination between 10 and 23° is particularly suitable, as noted by [41]. Additionally, inclined terrains are effective because they allow for denser packing of the arrays, thereby increasing productivity per unit area [42, 41]. If the angle is higher than 16° , the energy output per unit space increases by 48% [42]. This effect is valid and practical up to 33° [41]. In this context, regions were methodically excluded for north-east-west orientations with slopes exceeding 6.28° and for the south-facing aspect with slopes exceeding 33° . Visible in Figure 2a, this criterion excludes 68.48% of the eligible area.

Figure 2: Eligible areas for solar and wind energy.

2.2. Electricity Generation

In its previous version, GeoH2 only considered solar and wind energy for the production of green hydrogen. However, given Laos’s significant hydropower potential, it is essential to incorporate hydropower into the analysis.

The calculation of the capacity factor based on the ERA5 dataset is carried out in three processing steps: obtaining hourly run-off profiles through Atlite, determining the individual potential, and calculating the average within each hexagon. Atlite is an open source Python library that estimates hourly renewable power potentials [43]. Consequently, this process provides the input for the PyPSA optimisation.

The Laotian MEM provided hydropower data that include details on location, capacity, anticipated output, commercial operating date, head, and hydropower type; run-of-river or reservoir. Due to the unavailability of exact hydraulic head, a new framework was developed to estimate the hydraulic head. Supplementary material 1.3 gives an overview of the new methodology. Figure 3 illustrates the hydropower capacity installed by the year 2025, along with the anticipated additions up to the year 2030. Furthermore, it presents the installed capacity and delineates three regions within Laos.

Figure 3: Hydropower dams in Laos based on data provided by the Ministry of Energy and Mines Laos.

Hydropower Potential based on ERA5 Values. The estimation of hydropower output P is based on

$$P = Q \times H \times \eta \times \rho \times g \quad (2)$$

with Q being the flow rate, H the head, η plant efficiency, ρ the density of water, and g the standard acceleration of gravity. The plant efficiency η is assumed to be 74%, consistent with the average plant efficiency observed in Nepal [44]. The flow rate Q (in m^3/s) is calculated by

$$Q = R \times A \quad (3)$$

with the runoff R in m/s , and the catchment basin A in m^2 . The flow rate Q is estimated with Atlite weather data, which computes an inflow time series for the plant by aggregating over a given catchment basin. The basin is based on the hydrobasin model from Hydrosheds [45].

In the context of PyPSA optimisation, both the installed capacity and capacity factor are prerequisite parameters. The installed capacity is derived from the MEM data set. The capacity factor is determined by dividing the potential by the installed capacity and constraining the factor to not exceed the rated capacity. This analysis is performed on an hourly basis over the course of a year.

The individual capacities and capacity factors of hydropower plants must be joined for each hexagon. This is done with a spatial join between the hydropower plant locations and the hexagon grid to associate each plant with the corresponding hexagon:

$$\text{Mapping : } H_i \rightarrow \text{Hexagon}_j, \quad \text{if Plant } H_i \text{ is within Hexagon } j \quad (4)$$

This ensures that each plant was mapped to the hexagon that contains it. The capacity factor for each hexagon CF_{hex} is calculated with a weighed average by

$$CF_{\text{hex}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (CF_i \cdot W_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i} \quad (5)$$

with the capacity factor of each plant i , and its total capacity W_i as weight. This process is repeated until each hexagon has a hydro profile. If a hexagon does not contain a hydropower plant, its value is zero.

The hydro profile, comprising the capacity factors for each hexagon, is used in the PyPSA optimisation along with the wind and solar profiles to meet the hydrogen demand.

Hydropower potential based on empirical values. The MEM provided monthly electricity generation data for each plant covering the period 2019 to 2023. Here 2019 and 2022 are used, being respectively identified as a dry year and a wet year, respectively. A two-step imputation method was used for future hydropower dams lacking generation data: (1) averaging hourly generation data from plants in the same basin and to fill remaining gaps (2) identifying nearby plants within the closest radius. Each power plant was linked to a specific hydrological basin, and future plants were assigned the average capacity factor of that basin. If there were still plants without data after this basin-level averaging, nearby plants within an increasing radius were identified. The average hourly generation of these neighbouring plants was then used to fill in the missing data.

2.3. Domestic Electricity Demand

The electricity demand for 2021 was available as an hourly average for each day over the months (Supplementary material X.X). It was split into three areas: north, central and south, as visible in Figure 3. This was revised for 2025 and 2030, with the Ministry of Energy and Minerals projecting a rise in electricity demand by 36.71% in 2025 and by 80.4% in 2030 relative to the levels in 2021.

Meeting local electricity demand is a priority. To calculate the availability of power generation for green hydrogen production, the weighted demand was subtracted from the actual hourly generation of each hydropower plant. This approach is reasonable because electricity in Laos is almost entirely generated by hydropower. The hourly demand was then distributed proportionally according to each plant's share of the total installed capacity, ensuring an appropriate demand distribution among power plants.

2.4. Scenarios

The model was applied to four drivers, producing 24 scenarios as shown in Table 1. The difference between utilising hydropower exclusively for hydrogen production (total) and the current practice in which hydropower plants first meet electricity demand, with the surplus being used for hydrogen production (net). The two main types of electrolyser technology considered are alkaline electrolyte membrane (ALK) and polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) electrolysers, which have distinct CAPEX and baseline loads at 15% for ALK and 5% for PEM [46]. In this context, total generation scenarios are run without the baseload, whereas net generation includes it, highlighting the

stricter constraint of net generation. Empirical data on hydropower genera-

	Electrolyser Technology	Runoff Variability	2025	2030
Total Generation	PEM	Dry	T1	T7
		Wet	T2	T8
		ATLITE	T3	T9
	ALK	Dry	T4	T10
		Wet	T5	T11
		ATLITE	T6	T12
Net Generation	PEM	Dry	N1	N7
		Wet	N2	N8
		ATLITE	N3	N9
	ALK	Dry	N4	N10
		Wet	N5	N11
		ATLITE	N6	N12

Table 1: Analysed scenarios across the four drivers

tion for a dry and wet year, obtained from the MEM, is used and compared with the five-year average of theoretical runoff data obtained from the ERA5 data set [30]. This analysis is essential for highlighting differences not just between the dry (November to April) and wet (May to October) seasons, but also in annual variability, which can show considerable differences. Finally, a cost comparison is presented for the years 2025 and 2030. This is due to the anticipated commissioning of substantial new hydropower plant capacity by the year 2030. To facilitate a comparative analysis across all 940 hexagons, each hexagon is required to meet a demand of 1000 tons of hydrogen. It is assumed that all years have 8760 hours, omitting the 29th of February in leap years.

3. Results

The following results highlight the differences among the four drivers: electrolyser technology, runoff data, year, and electricity demand. Presented are the total generation results, followed by the net generation results, expressed in terms of LCOH in US dollars per kilogramme of hydrogen (USD/kgH₂).

3.1. Scenarios with Total Electricity Generation

Assuming that hydropower plants are fully available for hydrogen production, results in Figures 4a-f. The grey hexagons indicate that the hexagon

Figure 4: LCOH map for wet, dry and Atlite output of ALK and PEM in 2025.

could not produce the required 1000 tons of hydrogen despite using the maximum solar, wind, and any available hydro capacity. This is in part due to

overlap with neighbouring countries, resulting in substantial exclusion zones for solar and wind placement within these hexagons. The grey hexagons in the inner northern region are the result of expansive biodiversity conservation and forest protection zones. In scenarios T1 to T12, slightly more than 200 hexagons are unfeasible. Most hexagons have a LCOH between 9 and 10 USD/kgH₂ with exceptions when hydropower is involved.

Figure 5: LCOH map for wet, dry and Atlite output of ALK and PEM in 2030.

Figures 5a-f visualise the scenarios for the year 2030 (T7-T12). Here, the LCOH values are lower, and especially the Atlite scenarios T9 and T12 clearly show the advantages of hydropower. However, none of the scenarios results in a LCOH below 4 USD/kgH₂, with the lowest costs occurring when hydropower is available and installed.

Examining the least-cost hexagons of ALK and PEM electrolyzers (T1-

Figure 6: Bar chart of the cost components within the LCOH of the total scenarios.

T12) shows significant similarities as shown in Figure 6. The first six scenarios show 2025 (T1-T6), while those on the right relate to 2030 (T7-T12). With capital expenditures (CAPEX) of 975,000\$ per MW for PEM and 875,000\$ for ALK, the ALK scenarios consistently have a lower LCOH, primarily due to the cheaper electrolyser cost component. The primary difference between ALK and PEM in total generation scenarios lies in the electrolyser costs. An anomaly in the dry year data (T1,T4) indicates a higher installation of the battery capacity for PEM compared to ALK. This pattern continues for 2030, where both PEM dry (T7) and PEM Atlite (T9) feature elevated battery installations. In both scenarios, the least expensive hexagon is identical, leading to the assumption that the higher cost of the PEM versus the ALK electrolyser results in competitive battery costs. The cheapest LCOH costs for all scenarios are in the wet year (T8, T11) with 3.9 USD/kg for ALK and 3.99 with PEM electrolyser.

Figures 7a-f show the installed capacities of hydro, solar, and wind under the PEM scenarios in 2025 and 2030. The capacities are relatively comparable between the two electrolyses and the two years. Significant solar capacity is installed when hydropower is not available. In 2030, there is a reduction in wind power installation. Wind capacity is used only when required to satisfy demand, due to the low photovoltaic costs and high solar irradiance in Laos. Interestingly, hydropower is often not installed to its maximum available capacity, which is related to runoff variability.

Figure 7: Capacity map of hydro, solar, and wind for PEM in 2025 and 2030

Runoff variability has a significant impact on the LCOH. This is visible not only in Figure 6 with its high share in LCOH, but also in the varying average capacity factors shown in Figure 8. The hourly capacity factor for both dry and wet is smoother than the 5Y average values, as it is derived from interpolated monthly values. The theoretical 5-year average (Atlite) peaks highest, but shows significant seasonality. During the dry season, its level is surprisingly lower than that of a dry year, which is why the LCOH does not fall below that observed in the wet year. Therefore, additional capacities must be installed, as hydropower generation is notably disrupted during the dry season, requiring the reliance on other generation; in this model solar energy. The evaluation of LCOH for dry and wet years, as shown in Figure

6, further highlights this risk, as LCOH can almost double the price from a wet year to a dry year. This effect is reduced in 2030 to a mere 70% price increase.

Figure 8: Capacity factors using runoff from dry, wet, or Atlite

Figure 9: Net generation capacity of existing hydropower plants in 2025 and 2030

3.2. Scenarios with Net Electricity Generation

Subtracting the electricity demand from the hydropower generation (net generation) results in lower availability for hydrogen production. Figure 9

Figure 10: LCOH map for wet, dry and Atlite output of ALK and PEM in 2030.

illustrates the net generation capacity of all hydropower plants in 2025 and 2030 during the wet and dry years. The lines are perceived as thick due to fluctuations in demand between day and night.

By 2030, the projected increase in electricity demand reduces net hydropower generation, thereby reducing the availability of electricity for hydrogen production. This is especially visible in the northern and central regions, while the southern region sees minimal effects from this. When electricity demand exceeds generation, this gap is filled through imports from neighbouring countries.

During dry years, seasonal variations are more pronounced, whereas in wet years, they remain more consistent. In addition, during dry years, the northern region shows stronger seasonality compared to other regions. Due to

the higher population density, the northern and central regions of Laos have decreased net electricity generation as a result of increased demand, with inverse behaviour in the southern region. However, satisfying the electricity demand through hydropower sources remains the cheapest LCOH compared to solar or wind alone.

The hexagon maps for 2030 are presented in Figures 10a-f. Accounting for the baseload of ALK and PEM makes over 600 hexagons unfeasible, particularly impacting those lacking hydropower. This leaves slightly more than 300 hexagons with LCOH values. No clear geographical clustering of feasible hexagons is observed. However, maintaining a generation consistently above the given baseload for ALK and PEM remains largely impractical for most hexagons, even with solar and wind installations. Feasible hexagons frequently implement solar, wind, and high battery capacities.

Figure 11: Cost distribution of net and total generation scenarios

This leads to a significant increase in LCOH values in all net generation scenarios (N1-12). Figure 11 illustrates this, with 11a providing a comprehensive overview and 11b providing a detailed look at the same graph. Predictably, all comparable net generation scenarios have higher LCOH compared to total generation. As a consequence of the integrated baseload within

the net generation scenarios, a larger number of hexagons exhibit high LCOH values, while the overall generation without a baseload plateaus.

In most scenarios, the least expensive hexagon is an anomaly and is typically succeeded by a significant increase in LCOH, visible in 11b. As noted previously, this is primarily due to hydropower and their differing runoff. For the year 2025, 77 hexagons have hydropower potential, whereas for 2030, this number increases to 87 hexagons. Consequently, some hexagons contain more than one hydropower plant. Figure 11a shows that in total generation scenarios, the LCOH initially rises and then stagnates at 100 kt, corresponding to 100 hexagons. This could potentially signal that the seasonality of most hydropower plants is not suitable for hydrogen production as implemented here. As stated in Chapter 2.4, the requirement of 1000 tons is evenly spread across every hour with no option to postpone any hourly demand. This is a rigid implementation and poses drawbacks for renewable energy generation.

Figure 12: Bar chart of the cost components within the LCOH of the net scenarios.

Analysing Figure 12, which shows the cost components of the cheapest hexagon in all net generation scenarios (N1-N12), reveals that hydropower is installed only in the wet and Atlite scenarios. In all net scenarios (N1-N12), installations occur solely in the central and southern regions, as the high demand in the northern region makes net generation from hydropower less competitive compared to solar and wind for hydrogen production. In the wet 2025 scenario for PEM and ALK (N2, N5), the installed hydropower

capacity exceeds 120 MW, once again attributed to the Don Sahong dam. In contrast, in the dry scenario, no hydropower capacity was installed for hydrogen production at the Nam Ou dams located in the north of the country, because there was no surplus electricity available. This is a consequence of the high electricity demand in the northern region.

Looking further at the scenarios for 2030, reveals that for the wet year a much higher share of the LCOH comes from solar installations. However, LCOH for PEM and ALK is only reduced by 3.6% and 5.3% compared to 2025. The difference between the scenarios from wet to dry (N1, N2, N4, N5) remains large in 2025 with an increase of 47.8% for PEM and 55.6% for ALK. In 2030 this gap is closer with an increase of 19.5% and 30% for PEM and ALK, respectively (N7, N8, N10, N11).

4. Discussion

In Laos, climate change and natural disasters pose a persistent and significant risk [11, 47]. Taking into account only the variability of runoff, this can subsequently impact the profitability of adjacent industries; in this study, hydrogen production. The minimum LCOH of 3.9 USD/kgH₂ is achieved in the total generation scenario using an ALK electrolyser during a wet year in 2030, followed by the PEM electrolyser with LCOH of 3.99 USD/kgH₂. This is done under optimal conditions; however, it can increase substantially if different runoff data is used. The difference in runoff between a dry year (2019) and a wet year (2022) in Laos indicates significant cost variations for LCOH, with the largest being a two-fold increase to above 8 USD/kgH₂ and the smallest being a 16% increase. Hydropower is influenced by climate change, and it is anticipated that extremes in runoff will become more frequent rather than less, as indicated by [48, 49, 50]. The variability of runoff is therefore the main risk and factor affecting the profitability of hydrogen production in Laos.

Net generation scenarios show a more realistic scenario by subtracting the electricity demand from the available hydropower. This results in an increased LCOH, and, in particular, the northern and central regions are less attractive due to their higher population density, which in turn leads to greater electricity demand. The lower electricity demand in the south makes this region especially attractive if hydropower is not available exclusively for hydrogen production. Taking into account the results of this study, it could be beneficial to change the order of priority of electricity supply for specified

hydropower plants: shifting from meeting domestic electricity demand to hydrogen production. The Don Sahong dam, which frequently appeared in various scenarios as having the lowest LCOH, could serve as an effective test case. This would provide a stable baseload for hydrogen production while still allowing for electricity generation. In order to advance, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive examination of the impacts on the security of domestic electricity supply, alongside an evaluation of the profitability of exporting hydrogen in comparison to electricity.

From the results across all scenarios, it becomes clear that a majority of hexagons can not produce hydrogen at a competitive price. This can be attributed to the performance of the analysed generators. Wind power installations are rarely observed within the model and do not exhibit cost-effectiveness comparable to that of solar power. Even with reduced costs in 2030, this barely changes, and it can be concluded that wind energy within this model is not attractive. Solar power is the most installed generator. This can be primarily attributed to its lower assumed CAPEX, coupled with its extensive availability, as solar panels can be installed on 31% of Laos; double the amount of wind energy. In the context of Laos, solar energy represents the most accessible renewable energy source. According to the current Laos power development plan, solar capacity is projected to increase by 15.6 GW [51]. However, this does not imply that it yields low LCOH values.

The minimal LCOH calculated in this study differs from the LCOH range of 1.8 to 3.2 USD/kgH₂ cited in the Green Hydrogen Roadmap of the Lao-tian government that is being developed [52]. This is attributed to varying methodologies, and it is crucial to emphasize the limitations within the current article. Firstly, uniformly distributing demand across hours without allowing delay poses a significant disadvantage for renewable energy sources due to their substantial fluctuation. Secondly, including grid capacity can decrease electricity generation by balancing fluctuations. With hydropower currently dominating the generation capacity, the impact may be minimal. However, in future scenarios characterised by a significant increase in planned solar capacity, there is potential to decrease the Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH). Thirdly, the division of hexagons results in varying numbers of hydropower plants per hexagon, which affects the LCOH. This affects the LCOH of a hexagon, and adjusting the placement of hexagons could result in a higher available hydropower capacity and consequently lower costs. This model already accounts for existing Laotian PPAs to export electricity to its Asean neighbours. However, it does not include future extensions of these

PPAs and new PPAs that come into effect after 2030. Those are outside the scope of this work.

5. Conclusion

This research offers a comprehensive spatial-temporal assessment of the potential for green hydrogen production in Laos, highlighting the crucial role of hydropower in combination with the supporting roles of solar and wind energy. By integrating hydropower, solar and wind resources within a 940 hexagon grid and employing open-source tools like PyPSA, we estimate the LCOH under different scenarios that consider electrolyser technology, variability in runoff and projected electricity demand for 2025 and 2030.

Key findings indicate that wet year scenarios with alkaline electrolysers yield the lowest LCOH values, reaching 3.9 USD/kgH₂ in optimal cases. Hydropower, due to its regional abundance, plays a crucial role in reducing costs, although its seasonal variability significantly affects feasibility. Solar energy emerges as the most frequently installed resource, benefiting from lower capital cost and extensive availability, whereas wind energy contributes minimally due to limited cost effectiveness within this context.

This research underscores the potential for Laos to leverage its renewable energy resources to produce green hydrogen in a cost-effective way, supporting domestic fertiliser needs, improving energy export value and contributing to regional energy security. Future studies should address identified limitations to refine LCOH estimates and better inform policy and investment strategies.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Lukas Schirren: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Data curation, Visualizations, Writing – Original draft, review & editing, **Adam Hawkes:** Conceptualisation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Project administration & funding acquisition, **John Ward:** Writing – review & editing, **Sounthisack Phommachanh:** Writing – review & editing, **Vignesh Sridharan:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability statement

Data for this study is provided in the supplementary material and on GitHub. Data preparation details are at <https://github.com/lukasschirren/GeoH2-prep-Laos>. The research code is available at <https://github.com/lukasschirren/GeoH2-Laos>. An interactive dashboard with all scenarios is at <https://greenhydrogen-laos.streamlit.app/>.

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